

Knowledge Management Process And Employee Performance

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ABSTRACT

This research was conducted to determine the knowledge management process that exists in the Semen Indonesia Group companies, namely PT Semen Gresik, PT Semen Padang, PT Semen Tonasa. The knowledge management process can be carried out by creating knowledge, sharing knowledge and reusing knowledge. This research method is a comparative study, by collecting available information, so that researchers can find out how the process and development of knowledge management is in the research object. Knowledge creation at Semen Indonesia Group involves the transformation of information into products which can be facilitated by various departments such as the Director of Business Strategy, Production, Projects and Planning. This process can be effective, with factors such as internal innovation, autonomy, creative chaos, and layoffs. Knowledge sharing/transfer in groups includes serial, short distance, long distance, strategic and competency transfer. Knowledge management, which includes continuous learning, is essential for organizations to effectively manage and transfer critical information. Of the three processes in knowledge management at Semen Indonesia Group, the knowledge reuse process in capturing and documenting knowledge is still not fully implemented. In its implementation it has gone well but has not been fully documented. It is recommended that management update documentation for the reuse of knowledge. It is also recommended that this research be used as a basis or reference so that it can be used as a quantitative research hypothesis to produce different further research.

Key words: *Knowledge Management, Knowledge sharing, Performance*

INTRODUCTION

Information is the basis for someone to make decisions. Different information causes people to make different decisions. Someone who has knowledge makes decisions more effectively than someone who does not have knowledge (Drucker, 1998). Apart from being owned by individuals, information is also owned by organizations and is the basis for decision making. In organizations, knowledge is an important strategic resource, especially in rapidly changing environmental conditions (Davenport and Prusak, 1998; Nonaka, 2007). Competence must be managed as a strategic resource. Fajar (2009) found that the aim of knowledge management is to increase company profits through communication and improve knowledge management through knowledge transfer (knowledge sharing). Sharing information can help companies deal with business processes, problems that occur in each work unit, and share experiences about things outside of work which are useful for developing the knowledge of company employees.

A process that helps organizations identify, select, organize, distribute and communicate important information and experiences that are part of the organization (Viju Matthew, 2011). We are entering the Industrial 4.0 era, we live in a global world characterized by the speed of information. to transmit without wide geographic boundaries over the Internet. The emerging consequence of globalization is a knowledge-based economy, where effective human resource management is essential to ensure that workers continue to create relevant added value for the economy. Currently, organizations no longer compete solely based on capital and financial strength, but knowledge is a new competitive advantage in business life. This knowledge-based economy requires the implementation of good knowledge management practices to increase organizational efficiency. In general, information management represents the processes and practices carried out in a company, the aim of which is to unleash its intellectual potential, increase the effectiveness and efficiency of managing organizational information resources (Andreeva and Kianto, 2012; Gold, Malhotra). and Segars, 2001 Heisig, 2009). Differences in knowledge bases and companies' abilities to use and develop knowledge are one of the determining factors for company performance (Grant, 1996). However, many people, reviewing the academic literature on this issue, point out the real relationship between knowledge management (KM) and organizational performance (Andreeva and Kianto, 2012) and propose hypothetical relationships between aspects of knowledge management and organizational performance (Adams) and Lamont, 2003 ; Chapman and Magnusson, 2006) and case studies of highly successful KM implementation (Zaim, Tatoglu and Zaim, 2007). The situation is changing with the emergence of empirical studies evaluating the impact of KM on performance in larger samples of companies (Kianto, 2011; Marqués and Garrigós-Simón, 2006; M. Zack, McKeen and Singh, 2009).

The phenomenon after changing companies was caused by differences in knowledge of each subsidiary of the Semen Indonesia group. Differences in knowledge, such as new technological innovations from one subsidiary, can then be shared with respective subsidiaries that have not yet implemented the innovation. The aim of this research is to create a model that describes the Semen Indonesia Group information management process. Models are created to develop proposals. One of the most important factors in information management is the creation and transmission of information within an organization. These two processes influence organizational success and competitiveness (Syed-Ikhsan and Rowland, 2004). According to Andreas Budihardjo (2016), the knowledge management process basically consists of three

main activities, namely knowledge creation, knowledge sharing, and knowledge recycling. According to Nonaka (2007), knowledge creation is the development of new ideas through explicit and tacit knowledge. Knowledge creation helps companies improve management processes, identify new opportunities and support growth-enhancing innovation (Popadiuk and Choo, 2006). According to Nonaka and Takeuchi (1995), communication through the creation or transformation of knowledge is called SECI (socialization, externalization, integration and internalization). According to Subagyo (2007, p. 3), sharing is a method or step in knowledge management that is used to provide opportunities for members of a group, organization, agency or company to share technical knowledge, experiences and ideas. to other members. Information recycling involves reusing existing information to complete a job. The use of technology can help recycle information which is usually in the form of tools for storing or retrieving information. The effectiveness of information use once again depends on employees' knowledge and information acquisition (Szulanski, 2003).

Tacid Knowledge	Explicit Knowledge
<i>Knowledge of Experience</i>	<i>Knowledge of rationality</i>
<i>Simultaneous knowledge</i>	<i>Sequential knowledge</i>
<i>Analog knowledge</i>	<i>Digital knowledge</i>

Source : Nonaka, et al (1995)

Tacid Knowledge Versus Explicit Knowledge

<i>Tacid knowledge</i>	<i>Explicit Knowledge</i>
Ability to adapt, face new and extraordinary situations	Ability to deploy, recreate, access and deploy across the organization
Skills, know-how, know-why, and care-why	Kemampuan untuk mengajar, melatih
Ability to work together, share vision, and transmit culture	Ability to organize, structure, translate vision into mission statements, operational guidelines
Training and advising to transfer experiential knowledge on a one-to-one, face-to-face basis	Transfer knowledge through products, services, and documentation processes.

Source : Dalkir (2011:10)

Performance appraisal is a formal system for reviewing and evaluating an individual's or team's performance on a task. This allows employees to capitalize on their strengths and overcome identified weaknesses, helping them become more satisfied and productive employees. Although team performance assessment is very important when there are teams in an organization, the focus of performance measurement in most companies is still on individual employees. Mondy and Martocchio (2016) define organizational effectiveness as the level of success of an organization in achieving its goals. Most managers rely on PA techniques to provide feedback, encourage performance improvements, make informed decisions, justify firings, identify training and development needs, and defend HR decisions, such as why one employee got a higher raise than another. There are several ways to evaluate employee performance. It is important to group them into categories according to what you want to measure. Mondy and Martocchio (2016) divided performance measurement methods into four broad categories: trait systems, benchmark systems, behavioral systems, and performance-based systems. Miner (2002) suggests several aspects of efficiency, including: (a) quality produced, number of errors, time and accuracy in completing tasks, (b) quantity produced, referring to how many products or services can be produced, (c) work time, which examines the number of absences, lateness, and length of work a worker has, and (d) cooperation, which examines how a person helps or hinders the efforts of his colleagues.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Knowledge Management

Knowledge Management (KM) can be defined as the explicit and systematic management of vital knowledge and related processes for creating, collecting, organizing, diffusion, use and exploitation. This requires transforming personal knowledge into corporate knowledge that can be shared widely throughout the organization and applied appropriately (Skyrme & Amidon, 1997). KM is considered an integrated and systematic approach to identifying, managing, and sharing organizational knowledge and makes it possible for employees to create new knowledge collectively and thereby help achieve organizational goals (Mathew, 2008).

Today's society has many advantages in an information-rich era of competition in society and markets. The demand for information and knowledge has been expressed in various forums, committees and conferences that can guarantee socio-economic development and be able to produce new sustainable systems that have been eroded over time. The term "knowledge" has been used many times in research, consulting, management, industry and academia but many times the process of generating and using knowledge for value addition has not been thought through. Many researchers and scholars emphasize on knowledge resources and its application in daily life that makes a big difference. Because "knowledge is considered an asset in its possession" it is necessary to pay attention to its benefits for society, business and individuals. Vast amounts of money and resources have been provided to manage knowledge for better, regular, and repeatable use in industry and business. Knowledge management projects are often expensive (Cabrera & Cabrera, 2002; Zack, 1999) and time consuming. Many market players in businesses such as IBM have put resources into codifying knowledge that has specialists and other technical resources.

The primary role of knowledge management is in identifying, capturing, sharing, transferring, intellectual beliefs and values to gain profits and generate new knowledge that

can enhance the growth and development of society as a whole. The development of information technology and systems plays a major role in capturing, sharing, disseminating, and storing intellectual capital and knowledge for the benefit of society and industry. Generic processes and influencing factors combine innovation, group effort, sharing and learning adding to the growth of knowledge and its management processes. Collaboration and relationships between various components are essential for sharing, transfer and innovation including various countries, communities and societies around the world will help solve various problems in global business and society.

According to Widayana (2005:14-15), there are two types of knowledge found in companies, namely as follows:

1. Tacit Knowledge is knowledge that mostly resides within the company. Tacit knowledge is something that we know and experience, but is difficult to express clearly and completely. Tacit knowledge is very difficult to transfer to other people, because this knowledge is stored within the company according to its competence.
2. Explicit Knowledge is knowledge and experience about "How To", which is explained in a straightforward and systematic manner. A concrete example is a machine operating manual or an explanation given by an instructor in a training program.

Organizational members may share personal knowledge but with certain concerns (Mathew, 2011). These threats will be perceived as less valuable if their knowledge is part of the organization's public domain which can reduce its sustainability within the organization. Research from Hanssen-Bauer & Snow (1996) shows that in organizations learning and knowledge management facilitate conditions including trust, interests, and shared language that encourage access to knowledgeable members (Brown & Duguid, 1991), and a culture characterized by autonomy, redundancy, required variation, intention, and fluctuation (Nonaka, 1994).

Skills, knowledge transfer, and sharing are necessary to engage in success with colleagues and are acquired through long-term relationships. It is very difficult to define separate elements, and close contact and interaction between individual components is often necessary to achieve the desired results of knowledge transfer. Li & Zhu (2009) have added factors influencing informal knowledge transfer and stated that opportunity, motive, and knowledge transfer capacity are the determining factors for informal knowledge transfer between individuals. Knowledge transfer depends largely on the people associated with the organization and the varying degrees of richness of channels and tasks for which each will be used. The knowledge transfer motive contains the transfer desires and reputation interests of each individual at various levels.

Information Systems

The definition of information systems according to Turban and Volonino (2010:11) is that information systems are processes that support companies in collecting, processing, storing and analyzing data and disseminating information throughout the organization. Meanwhile, according to Stair and Reynold (2010: 10), an information system is defined as a set of interrelated elements to be input, processed, stored and distributed in order to obtain feedback in meeting certain company goals. So it can be concluded that an information system is the process of collecting, processing, storing and analyzing data and disseminating information.

Knowledge Management Process

The division of the knowledge management process has many variations, experts divide it into several processes from creation to implementation in the organization. According to Tiawana (2000), information management is divided into three parts, namely. acquisition, distribution, and deletion of information. Kianto, Vanhala, and Heilman (2016) divide knowledge management into five aspects, namely knowledge acquisition, knowledge sharing, knowledge creation, knowledge codification, and knowledge preservation. Obtaining information is an activity where a person receives new information that is useful for improving work tasks. Next is sharing, namely the process of sharing knowledge which is also related to the social needs of each organization. Additionally, the creation of information provides an opportunity for individuals within the organization to participate in the development of new plans. This information creation activity encourages people to use their creativity. Furthermore, information coding is an activity that uses technology to strengthen information. In addition, information storage is an activity to preserve information in the sense that the continuity of information must be an invisible resource in the organization. Information preservation can increase the public's sense of recognition because experts or professionals participate in information preservation activities.

Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a pleasant emotional attitude towards work. This attitude is reflected in individual behavior when carrying out work tasks. According to Handoko (2007), job satisfaction is an individual assessment where assessments vary between individuals. According to Sondang and Siagiani (2006), job satisfaction is a person's position when evaluating work, this concerns the attitude achieved, namely attitude. positive and negative. This means that job satisfaction is an individual's assessment of the work experience they have in an organization. Measuring job satisfaction is based on the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) by Rene Davis, George England, and Lloyd Lofquist. (1964) Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) is the result of the development of Rene Davis, George England, and Lloyd Lofquist (1964). This measure of job satisfaction can describe work environment conditions that can motivate people to be more satisfied with their work. The six dimensions of the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) are achievement, comfort, space, altruism, security, autonomy.

The Influence of Knowledge Management on Job Satisfaction

In today's information era, to achieve good job satisfaction, companies must manage the information held by their employees. As in the previous statement, employee knowledge is a company asset. The company's goal is to implement information management for success at work. This is measured through five aspects of knowledge management, namely knowledge acquisition, knowledge sharing, knowledge creation, knowledge codification, knowledge retention (Kianto, Vanhala, & Heilman, 2016). These five management skills can help increase employee job satisfaction. By fulfilling job satisfaction, employees can participate in the company's development. Therefore, companies need to know the extent to which information management influences employee job satisfaction. Job satisfaction can be measured using the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) by Rene Davis, George England, and Lloyd Lofquist (1964). This article uses the case of Semen Indonesia Group. Analysis of knowledge

creation at Semen Indonesia Group. The creation or transformation of information enables the interaction of existing processes within the company. The creation of knowledge in the company is an innovation in product development that is managed not only with cement, but also with other building materials such as paint, reinforced concrete, coal, and others. The use of a soft crusher on the crane means installation is quicker. In addition, rotten milk products and rice husks are also used, the results of which are replaced by fuel and coal.

Enablers who support the information creation process are the Director of Business Development and Business Strategy, Director of Production, Director of Projects and Planning, Director of Marketing and Supply Chain, Director of Human Resources and Legal, and Director of Finance, among all their subordinates. Currently everything is well organized, namely projects and planning. With these five supporting factors, the knowledge creation process can run effectively. First, internal intentions, such as standards for evaluating the success of the information created, what percentage can be implemented. Second, autonomy is an original idea born from autonomous individuals, which spreads to teamwork and becomes an organizational idea, such as replacing movable bolts so they don't break often and internal hoists don't often die and stop. Third, creative chaos like Semen Padang (1910) which experienced a crisis but tried to survive and become stronger. Fourth, layoffs, like a cash pool, all the money is collected and can be used by small businesses in need. Fifth, diversity is needed, as a company that wants the International Semen University as a research institution.

Analysis of knowledge sharing/transfer at Semen Indonesia Group includes the concepts of serial transfer, short-distance transfer, long-distance transfer, strategic transfer, and competency transfer (Dixon, 2000). Serial transmission at Semen Indonesia is similar to carrying out work that has already been done and in a different context, namely. the engine got a one-turn throttle and was replaced with a more efficient engine starter. Similar to the first change, close transfer creates synergies for companies in production, markets, and so on. Telecommuting is like learning about patents, especially in the technology industry. In strategic transfer, the discovery of good ideas is carried out in a forum and then celebrated and rewarded, so that the discovery of these ideas does not stop with one person, but spreads to groups or business organizations. Expertise refers to groups that have technical problems in doing work, such as production costs, measuring raw materials and a good understanding of how to do the work.

Semen Indonesia Group's knowledge reuse analysis documents knowledge reuse and the reuse of existing knowledge. In implementing information reuse, Semen Indonesia management pays attention to the views of each subsidiary, for each available information it is estimated that each subsidiary has a certain percentage of successful implementation, however the company's internal documentation is not yet completely organized. Semen Indonesia Group's information management analysis is based on information creation, information sharing, and information recycling. The results of this research are important for management. Therefore, the knowledge management process requires continuous development of the latest knowledge so that existing company systems can be updated.

The application of knowledge management implemented at Semen Indonesia is by implementing a culture of continuous learning, which is a culture of sharing and learning.

Where its implementation has been carried out since 1995. With the aim of managing knowledge which is a high value asset in the company. The knowledge management activities carried out by Semen Indonesia do not have to start from formal activities, but can be started from informal activities such as communities of practice, shared learning and technology. This activity will lead to sharing knowledge until it becomes a decision. Meanwhile, technology will become a medium for disseminating knowledge sharing. The results of this research show that implementing knowledge management can help organizations find, select, organize, spread and transfer important knowledge or information needed by Semen Indonesia employees within the organization. The results of this research are also in accordance with Bergeron's theory (2003: 8-9) which emphasizes that knowledge management is a systematic and thoughtful business optimization strategy for selecting, filtering, storing, organizing and communicating important business information in a company aimed at improving employee performance, increasing innovation and the company's ability to share and learn

CONCLUSION

The Knowledge Management process at Semen Indonesia Group is carried out through knowledge creation, knowledge sharing/transfer (sharing/distributing knowledge) and knowledge reuse (reusing knowledge). In knowledge creation, creation is carried out through a process of socialization, externalization, combination and internalization carried out by the company. Then in knowledge sharing/transfer, knowledge is disseminated with new innovations not only for individual needs but also for companies. Furthermore, in knowledge reuse, knowledge that has been successfully implemented by the company can be used again for similar purposes with existing adjustments. Of the three processes in knowledge management at Semen Indonesia Group, the knowledge reuse process in capturing and documenting knowledge is still not fully implemented. In its implementation it has gone well but has not been fully documented. It is recommended that management update documentation for the reuse of knowledge. It is also recommended that this research be used as a basis or reference so that it can be used as a quantitative research hypothesis to produce different further research.

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